

Practical Methods for Analyzing and Visualizing QUIC Quality Assurance in Smartphone Apps

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Abstract:

This paper reports practical insights into addressing operational challenges in maintaining QUIC performance within mobile applications through the implementation and deployment of an integrated terminal-side analysis SDK. The proposed SDK enables real-time visualization of communication quality degradation factors from the client's perspective—an aspect that has been difficult to achieve with conventional server-centric offline analyses using tools such as qlog and qvis.

The SDK leverages ngtcp2 and nghttp3 to record all QUIC events with detailed nanosecond-level timestamps in a lightweight manner. On the Android platform, it also utilizes android.telephony.TelephonyManager to log radio metrics such as RSRP, RSRQ, SINR, and RSSI every 100 ms. By correlating these network and transport-level metrics, the SDK enables fine-grained performance evaluation and analysis of mobile applications—including the “last-mile” wireless segment—across multiple carriers and both iOS and Android devices.

The key practical findings obtained through this study are as follows:

- Quantitative characterization and visualization of quality variations caused by last-mile wireless environments and terminal configurations.
- Practical client-side quality evaluation and visualization for application types such as video streaming and gaming (API-based interactions).
- A practical client-side method for isolating and visualizing root causes of quality degradation events.

Keywords: QUIC, Smoothed RTT, Congestion Control

1. Introduction

In recent years, mobile applications such as video streaming services, online games, and social networking platforms have increasingly adopted QUIC and HTTP/3 protocols [3], [4], [5], [6] to enhance user experience. While QUIC offers several advantages—including faster connection establishment and the avoidance of Head-of-Line blocking through multiplexing—new operational challenges related to communication quality have emerged in real-world deployments.

For instance, because existing network infrastructures are primarily optimized for TCP, it is often difficult to isolate the root causes of issues such as handshake duplication delays, RTT degradation, and unstable congestion control when operating over QUIC. Even when users experience degraded quality, such as video playback interruptions or input latency in games, conventional server-side offline monitoring methods struggle to provide immediate diagnosis.

Moreover, most existing monitoring and analysis tools are designed for server-side measurements assuming TCP as the transport protocol, and thus have limited capability in capturing QUIC-specific congestion behavior. Interfaces and tools such as qlog and

qvis [1] mainly support offline server log analysis, which is not well suited for real-time observation of client-side network conditions or dynamic wireless environments.

In practice, there are cases where offline qlog analysis on the server fails to determine the cause of video quality degradation, yet combining it with client-side observations collected via our SDK reveals phenomena such as silent drops within the server's session buffering process. Furthermore, in mobile environments, communication quality can vary significantly across carriers due to differences in wireless conditions (e.g., concurrent session counts, radio characteristics). Since these conditions can only be directly measured on the client device, there are few frameworks that can effectively capture and correlate such information.

To address these operational challenges, this paper presents the implementation and deployment of a detailed QUIC analysis SDK that can be seamlessly integrated into smartphone applications. We report practical insights gained through its real-world use, focusing on methods for end-to-end quality visualization and analysis from the client perspective.

2. Practical Implementation Approach

In this study, we designed and implemented an SDK that enables observation of QUIC communication quality within smartphone applications. This section describes the design principles

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of the SDK, the technical challenges encountered during its implementation, and the corresponding solutions developed to address them.

Fig. 1: Application Protocol Stack

2.1 SDK Design Principles

Assuming deployment in real-world mobile applications, the SDK was designed based on the following principles:

- **Lightweight Implementation:** To minimize performance overhead under the resource constraints of mobile devices.
- **Comprehensive Coverage:** To record detailed QUIC events—including handshake, cryptographic operations, and congestion control—as well as radio signal metrics such as RSRP, RSRQ, SINR, and RSSI (on Android).
- **Real-Time Observability:** To support immediate troubleshooting and quality assessment through real-time monitoring.
- **Cross-Platform Integration:** To ensure operability and consistent behavior across both iOS and Android environments.

2.2 Technical Challenges and Solutions

During implementation, several challenges were encountered, including dependency complexity and environmental variability. The representative issues and their corresponding solutions are summarized in Table.1.

Table 1: Technical Challenges and Solutions in SDK Integration

Challenge	Solution
Dependency complexity	Identified stable combinations of dependent library versions and fixed them in the build scripts to ensure reproducibility.
Insufficient real-time observability	Traditional server-centric analysis made it difficult to capture the client’s runtime conditions. The proposed SDK was therefore integrated directly into mobile applications to collect QUIC events in real time from actual devices.
Environmental variability and instability	Incorporated a continuous testing process across diverse environments—such as emulators vs. real devices and Wi-Fi vs. mobile networks—to detect and resolve issues at an early stage.

2.3 Cross-Compilation

During the porting of the SDK to both iOS and Android platforms, challenges arose from differences in dependencies and build environments during cross-compilation. To address these issues, a stable toolchain was established through iterative testing, and all dependent libraries were statically linked with fixed versions. This approach ensured reproducible builds and improved the overall stability of the SDK across platforms.

3. SDK Deployment Methodology

This section describes the deployment methodology of the proposed SDK, which enables detailed analysis of QUIC events within smartphone applications. The deployment approach focuses on integrating the SDK seamlessly into mobile app environments while maintaining low overhead and ensuring consistent data collection across devices.

3.1 iOS/Android Integration

The proposed SDK was implemented by cross-compiling the major libraries that constitute the QUIC protocol—namely OpenSSL, libev, ngtcp2, and nghttp3 [7], [8], [9], [10]—and embedding them as static libraries within the mobile application. This design enables direct observation of QUIC behaviors such as handshake processes, cryptographic operations, and congestion control from within the application on the end device.

For the iOS platform, the integration utilized the Xcode toolchain in combination with the iOS-CMake toolchain, ensuring compatibility with the ARM64 architecture. The `-fembed-bitcode` compilation option was applied to comply with iOS deployment requirements and to maintain binary integrity during App Store distribution.

For Android, the integration employed the NDK’s CMake toolchain, with the target ABI fixed to `arm64-v8a` to achieve stable and reproducible builds across diverse device environments.

Table 2: Library Versions and Build Notes

Library	Notes
OpenSSL	(b2ac43b0d89b5b528941ad9d233b4cb4f99a7cca) Built as <code>libcrypto.a</code> and <code>libssl.a</code> .
libev	(93823e6ca699df195a6c7b8bfa6006ec40ee0003) Built as <code>libev.a</code> .
ngtcp2 / nghttp3	(601158748e194a765221f6523d0138b01058ff9e) Built as <code>libngtcp2.a</code> , <code>libnghttp3.a</code> , and <code>libngtcp2_crypto_oss1.a</code> . Shared libraries were disabled during CMake build configuration (<code>-DENABLE_SHARED=OFF</code>) to ensure portability and reproducibility.

3.2 Event Collection Logic

Within the SDK, all callback functions provided by ngtcp2 and nghttp3 are hooked to enable lightweight recording of various QUIC events, including handshake completion, cryptographic operations, ACK reception, and stream data transmission and reception. Each captured event is stored in a 128-bit structured format and can be either visualized via the graphical interface or transmitted incrementally to the cloud infrastructure. This mechanism enables real-time distributed logging and visualization of end-to-end QUIC behavior.

Through this design, the SDK allows direct observation of network conditions across the last-mile segment and application layer—areas that have been difficult to analyze with conventional server-centric log monitoring. As a result, it provides valuable insights into identifying the root causes of communication quality degradation.

Listing 1: RealTime QUIC Event Hooking ngtcp2

```

auto callbacks = ngtcp2_callbacks{
    .client_initial = ...,
    .recv_crypto_data = ...,
    .handshake_completed = ...,
    .recv_version_negotiation = ...,
    .encrypt = ...,
    .decrypt = ...,
    .hp_mask = ...,
    .recv_stream_data = ...,
    .acked_stream_data_offset = ...,
    .stream_close = ...,
    .recv_retry = ...,
    .extend_max_local_streams_bidi = ...,
    .rand = ...,
    .get_new_connection_id = ...,
    .update_key = ...,
    .path_validation = ...,
    .select_preferred_addr = ...,
    .stream_reset = ...,
    .extend_max_stream_data = ...,
    .handshake_confirmed = ...,
    .recv_new_token = ...,
    .delete_crypto_aead_ctx = ...,
    .delete_crypto_cipher_ctx = ...,
    .get_path_challenge_data = ...,
    .stream_stop_sending = ...,
    .version_negotiation = ...,
    .recv_rx_key = ...,
    .tls_early_data_rejected = ...,
};

```

Listing 2: RealTime QUIC Event Hooking nghttp3

```

nghttp3_callbacks callbacks{
    .stream_close = ...,
    .recv_data = ...,
    .deferred_consume = ...,
    .begin_headers = ...,
    .recv_header = ...,
    .end_headers = ...,
    .begintrailers = ...,
    .recv_trailer = ...,
    .endtrailers = ...,
    .stop_sending = ...,
    .reset_stream = ...,
    .recv_settings = ...,
    .recv_origin = ...,
    .end_origin = ...,
    .rand = ...,
};

```

Listing 3: RealTime QUIC Event Store

```

static inline void ANALYZE(int idx, size_t len) {
    std::lock_guard<std::mutex> lock(ANALYZE_LOCK__);
    ANALYZE_TIMES__.push_back({idx, client_timestamp(),
    len});
}

```

4. Operational Observation Data

This section introduces the data collected through real-world operation of the proposed SDK, which was integrated into a smartphone application and deployed under actual network conditions.

4.1 Measurement Conditions

The measurements were conducted under the following conditions:

- **Target Carriers:** Three mobile network operators (MNO-A, MNO-B, MNO-C)
- **Measurement Environments:** Public RAN environment and high-bandwidth office environment
- **Target Traffic:** 1 MB file download
- **Termination Methods:** Edge POP termination (remote and local origins) and direct termination via Nginx

4.2 Visualization of Measurement Results

The collected QUIC events included handshake processes, RTT variations, ACK retransmissions, and CWND expansion behavior. By visualizing these parameters in a temporal sequence, it became possible to identify latency factors and detect periods of bandwidth underutilization within each session.

Fig. 2: Event timeline of payload transmission under Edge POP termination with a remote origin.

Fig. 3: Event analysis of ACK behavior across carriers: remote origin (top) and local origin (bottom) in a high-bandwidth office RAN environment.

Fig. 4: Event analysis of ACK behavior across carriers: remote origin (top) and local origin (bottom) in a public RAN environment.

Table 3: Detailed Event Metrics: Remote 1MB Download

Event	MNO (A)	MNO (B)	MNO (C)
Remote / Public RAN			
Drop Count (NGTCP2_STREAM_LOSS_COUNT)	0	1	0
ACK Ratio (SENT_PACKET / RECV_PACKET)	127 / 764 (16.6%)	292 / 1049 (7.8%)	500 / 772 (64.7%)
MNO (A) / MNO (C)	Nearly continuous bidirectional transmission with minimal gaps; mostly streaming-like behavior (ACK-dominant).		
MNO (B)	Bursty and intermittent transmission pattern; tendency toward bulk transfer behavior.		
Radio Resource (RAN)	Total time cost observed to be similar across all carriers.		

Fig. 5: Module block diagram of payload transmission under Edge POP termination with a remote origin.

Fig. 6: Edge POP termination with remote origin: cache layer structure.

Table 4: Detailed Event Metrics: Local 1MB Download

Event	MNO (A)	MNO (B)	MNO (C)
Local / Public RAN			
Drop Count (NGTCP2_STREAM_LOSS_COUNT)	0	1	0
ACK Ratio (SENT_PACKET / RECV_PACKET)	71 / 765 (9.3%)	345 / 839 (41.1%)	324 / 769 (42.1%)
Inter-packet Interval (NGTCP2_RECV_STREAM)	p95 = 6.5 p99 = 45.2	p95 = 71.1 p99 = 277	p95 = 23.3 p99 = 137
MNO (A)	No significant issues observed; transmission considered stable.		
MNO (C)	Frequent ACKs and larger inter-packet gaps suggest retransmissions other than explicit drops.		
MNO (B)	A retransmission event was observed corresponding to NGTCP2_STREAM_LOSS_COUNT == 1.		

4.3 Measurement Results under Edge POP Termination

4.3.1 With Local Origin Placement

Fig. 7: Event timeline of payload transmission under Edge POP termination with a local origin.

Fig. 8: Edge POP termination with local origin: cache layer structure.

Fig. 9: Comparison of payload event timelines between local and remote origins under Edge POP termination.

Fig. 10: Event timeline of payload transmission under direct termination (Nginx HTTP/3).

Fig. 11: Module block diagram of direct termination via Nginx HTTP/3.

4.4 Differences in Measurements by Termination Method

In the Edge POP termination configuration, response caching contributed to reduced initial RTT. However, instances of traffic concentration were occasionally observed in the last-mile segment. In contrast, under Nginx direct termination, RTT values were generally higher, but the responses were more evenly distributed, exhibiting a time-sliced arrival pattern of data packets.

4.5 Importance of Real-World Observations

While no issues were detected in laboratory tests, sessions operating under actual mobile carrier networks exhibited handshake instability and frequent retransmissions. These findings indicate that certain operational issues cannot be fully captured in controlled lab environments alone, emphasizing the necessity of field observations in real-world mobile network conditions.

5. Practical Insights Derived from Observational Data

Building upon the measurement results presented in the previous section, this section summarizes practical insights obtained from operational observations. These findings do not represent generalized characteristics of all QUIC deployments; rather, they are specific to the conditions and environments used in this study.

5.1 Observations on Environmental Differences

A comparison between laboratory and real network environments revealed that sessions stable in simulator or Wi-Fi setups often exhibited handshake instability and frequent retransmissions under mobile carrier conditions. This suggests that testing solely in laboratory environments is insufficient, and that observations conducted in real networks—including last-mile segments—are essential for accurate assessment of QUIC performance.

5.2 Observations on Termination Methods and Origin Distance

When comparing Edge POP termination and Nginx direct termination, the former demonstrated smaller initial RTTs due to caching effects, but was more prone to traffic concentration in the last-mile segment. Conversely, the latter exhibited larger RTTs yet showed more evenly distributed response patterns, suggesting reduced congestion in edge environments.

5.3 Effectiveness of Client-Side Observation

Client-side observation enabled quantitative analysis of carrier-specific ACK response characteristics—differences that are difficult to capture solely through server-side logs such as *qlog*. In particular, significant variations in the ratio of transmitted to received packets were observed across mobile carriers, providing valuable insights for tuning and optimization based on carrier-specific network behavior.

In this study, ACK response ratios ranged widely from 16.6% to 64.7% depending on the carrier. A higher ACK ratio indicates that a larger number of acknowledgments are being sent from the client side, potentially reducing overall transmission efficiency. Based on prior operational experience, such behavior tends to become more pronounced when radio resources are limited, for example during spikes in the number of concurrently connected devices. However, since radio resource utilization is observable only at the base station level, this study does not provide direct verification of that relationship. Therefore, while this remains an area for future investigation, the results highlight that ACK response characteristics can vary significantly with radio resource conditions—an important consideration for practical communication efficiency evaluation.

- Carrier-specific variations in ACK response characteristics: large differences in packet transmission/reception ratios (16.6%–64.7%)
- Intermittent handshake failures under wireless environments
- Traffic concentration observed under Edge POP termination

6. Practical Impact of Operational Deployment

This section describes the practical effects and improvement cases observed when the developed SDK was applied in real-world operations. While the results presented here are derived from a specific service environment and may not be universally applicable, they may provide useful references for practitioners facing similar challenges.

6.1 Early Detection of Quality Issues

Through client-side observation enabled by the SDK, it became possible to detect phenomena that were difficult to identify with conventional server-centric monitoring alone. Specifically, the system revealed carrier-specific differences in ACK response characteristics (notable disparities in send/receive ratios) likely caused by temporal congestion at radio base stations, intermittent

handshake failures under mobile environments, and traffic concentration phenomena at Edge POP terminations. These insights contributed to earlier identification of potential quality degradation indicators.

6.2 Operational Process

The observational data collected through the SDK can be effectively utilized in operational workflows as follows:

- Rapid root cause analysis during communication quality degradation
- Comparative evaluation of communication quality impacts in A/B testing
- Providing reference information for quality verification during new feature releases

These cases suggest that incorporating client-side observation as a supplementary monitoring approach enables earlier problem detection and facilitates faster operational improvement.

7. Conclusion

This paper addressed practical challenges related to maintaining QUIC performance in mobile applications by designing and implementing a client-integrated analysis SDK and reporting findings from its deployment in real operational environments.

The key outcomes of this study are as follows:

- Developed an SDK compatible with both iOS and Android, capable of lightweight recording of all QUIC events—including handshake, congestion control—and radio signal metrics (for Android) for comprehensive analysis.
- Demonstrated that client-side observation can complement traditional server-centric monitoring by revealing environmental differences between lab and real networks, as well as quality variations among carriers and termination methods.
- Verified through use cases such as video streaming and gaming (HTTP/3 API calls) that client-side quality observation contributes to operational improvement and troubleshooting efficiency.

While the findings presented in this paper are not universally applicable to all environments, they provide valuable insights for practitioners dealing with communication quality issues in QUIC-based mobile applications. Future work includes expanding the observation scope and conducting further validation across different service environments to accumulate broader empirical knowledge.

8. Appendix

Listing 4: Tool Chain Repositories

```
git clone https://github.com/leetal/ios-cmake.git
git clone https://github.com/openssl/openssl.git
git clone git@github.com:enki/libev.git
git clone https://github.com/ngtcp2/ngtcp2.git
git clone https://github.com/ngtcp2/nghttp3.git
```

Listing 5: Build iOS

```
# openssl
IOS_SDK=$(xcrun --sdk iphoneos --show-sdk-path)
TARGET=ios64-xcrun

./Configure $TARGET \
    no-shared no-dso no-engine \
    --prefix=$PWD/../openssl-ios \
    --openssldir=$PWD/../openssl-ios \
    -fembed-bitcode \
    -mios-version-min=12.0

make -j
make install
# libev
cd libev
autoreconf -i

export SDK=$(xcrun --sdk iphoneos --show-sdk-path)
export CC="$(xcrun --sdk iphoneos -f clang) -arch arm64 -
    isysroot $SDK"
export CFLAGS="-O2 -fembed-bitcode"

./configure --host=arm-apple-darwin --disable-shared --
    enable-static CC="$CC" CFLAGS="$CFLAGS"
make -j

# ngtcp2
autoreconf -i
mkdir -p _build && cd _build

cmake .. \
    -DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=~/.git/ios-cmake/ios.toolchain.
cmake \
    -DPLATFORM=OS64 \
    -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release \
    -DENABLE_LIB_ONLY=ON \
    -DENABLE_SHARED=OFF \
    -DENABLE_OPENSSL=ON \
    -DOPENSSL_USE_STATIC_LIBS=TRUE \
    -DOPENSSL_ROOT_DIR=~/.git/openssl-ios \
    -DOPENSSL_CRYPTOLIBRARY=~/.git/openssl-ios/lib/libcrypto
.a \
    -DOPENSSL_SSL_LIBRARY=~/.git/openssl-ios/lib/libssl.a \
    -DOPENSSL_INCLUDE_DIR=~/.git/openssl-ios/include \
    -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=./install-ios

make -j
make install

# nghttp3
autoreconf -i
mkdir -p _build && cd _build

cmake .. \
    -DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=~/.git/ios-cmake/ios.toolchain.
cmake \
    -DPLATFORM=OS64 \
    -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release \
    -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=./install-ios

make -j
make install
```

Listing 6: Build Android

```
export ANDROID_NDK_ROOT=~/.Library/Android/sdk/ndk
    /26.2.11394342
export TOOLCHAIN=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/toolchains/llvm/
    prebuilt/darwin-x86_64
export TOOLCHAIN_FILE=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/build/cmake/
    android.toolchain.cmake
export API=29

# OpenSSL
export ANDROID_NDK_ROOT=~/.Library/Android/sdk/ndk
```

```

/26.2.11394342
export TOOLCHAIN=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/toolchains/llvm/
prebuilt/darwin-x86_64
export PATH=$TOOLCHAIN/bin:$PATH
export API=29
export AR=llvm-ar
export CC=aarch64-linux-android$API-clang
export CXX=aarch64-linux-android$API-clang++

./Configure android-arm64 \
  -D__ANDROID_API__=$API \
  --prefix=$PWD/../openssl-android \
  --openssldir=$PWD/../openssl-android \
  no-shared \
  no-tests

make
make install

# libev
export ANDROID_NDK_ROOT=~/.Library/Android/sdk/ndk
/26.2.11394342
export TOOLCHAIN=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/toolchains/llvm/
prebuilt/darwin-x86_64
export PATH=$TOOLCHAIN/bin:$PATH
export TARGET=aarch64-linux-android
export API=29
export AR=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-ar
export AS=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-as
export CC=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/aarch64-linux-android$API-clang
export CXX=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/aarch64-linux-android$API-clang
++
export LD=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/ld.11d
export STRIP=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-strip
export RANLIB=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-ranlib
export CFLAGS="--target=$TARGET -fPIC -fvisibility=default"
export LDFLAGS="--target=$TARGET"

autoreconf -i
./configure \
  --host=$TARGET \
  --enable-static \
  --disable-shared \
  CC="$CC" \
  CFLAGS="$CFLAGS -fPIC"

make

# ngtcp2
export ANDROID_NDK_ROOT=~/.Library/Android/sdk/ndk
/26.2.11394342
export TOOLCHAIN=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/toolchains/llvm/
prebuilt/darwin-x86_64
export TOOLCHAIN_FILE=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/build/cmake/
android.toolchain.cmake
export PATH=$TOOLCHAIN/bin:$PATH
export API=29
export AR=llvm-ar
export CC=aarch64-linux-android$API-clang
export CXX=aarch64-linux-android$API-clang++
export AR=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-ar
export RANLIB=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-ranlib
#
autoreconf -i
mkdir -p ./_build_android
cd _build_android

cmake .. \
  -DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=$TOOLCHAIN_FILE \
  -DANDROID_ABI=arm64-v8a \
  -DANDROID_PLATFORM=android-29 \
  -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release \
  -DENABLE_LIB_ONLY=ON \
  -DENABLE_SHARED=OFF \
  -DENABLE_OPENSSL=ON \

```

```

-DOPENSSL_USE_STATIC_LIBS=TRUE \
-DOPENSSL_ROOT_DIR=~/.git/openssl-android \
-DOPENSSL_CCRYPTO_LIBRARY=~/.git/openssl-android/lib/
libcrypto.a \
-DOPENSSL_SSL_LIBRARY=~/.git/openssl-android/lib/libssl.a \
-DOPENSSL_INCLUDE_DIR=~/.git/openssl-android/include \
-DENABLE_GNUTLS=OFF \
-DENABLE_WOLFSSL=OFF \
-DENABLE_BORINGSSL=OFF \
-DCMAKE_TRY_COMPILE_TARGET_TYPE=STATIC_LIBRARY \
-DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=../install-android

make -j
make install

# nghttp3
export ANDROID_NDK_ROOT=~/.Library/Android/sdk/ndk
/26.2.11394342
export TOOLCHAIN=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/toolchains/llvm/
prebuilt/darwin-x86_64
export TOOLCHAIN_FILE=$ANDROID_NDK_ROOT/build/cmake/
android.toolchain.cmake
export PATH=$TOOLCHAIN/bin:$PATH
export API=29
export AR=llvm-ar
export CC=aarch64-linux-android$API-clang
export CXX=aarch64-linux-android$API-clang++
export AR=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-ar
export RANLIB=$TOOLCHAIN/bin/llvm-ranlib

autoreconf -i
mkdir -p _build_android
cd _build_android

cmake .. \
  -DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=$TOOLCHAIN_FILE \
  -DANDROID_ABI=arm64-v8a \
  -DANDROID_PLATFORM=android-29 \
  -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release \
  -DENABLE_LIB_ONLY=ON \
  -DENABLE_SHARED=OFF \
  -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=../install-android

make -j
make install

```

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- [8] nghttp3 Project. <https://github.com/ngtcp2/nghttp3.git>
- [9] OpenSSL Project. <https://github.com/openssl/openssl.git>
- [10] libev Project. <https://github.com/enki/libev.git>